

High Power Photodiodes for Photonics Technology in Naval Applications

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INTRODUCTION

High-power photodiodes are required for numerous applications of photonics technology in radio-frequency (RF) systems. Shown in Fig. 1(a) is a RF system employing a photonic link connected directly to a receive-mode antenna. Such photonic front-ends require high-power photodiodes to achieve low noise figure for high-sensitivity applications. A receive-mode RF system utilizing photonic signal processing is depicted in Fig. 1(b). These implementations require high linearity, which will typically be characteristic of a high-power photodiode. Finally, Fig. 1(c) shows a photonic link in the transmit path that can function as an RF power amplifier.

Fig. 1. RF architectures employing high-power photodiodes. (a) Photonic front end (II). (b) Photonic signal processing (III). (c) Photonic amplifier (IV). ADC: analog-to-digital converter, AWG: arbitrary waveform generator, E/O: electrical-to-optical converter.

LOW NOISE FIGURE PHOTONIC FRONT ENDS

Fig. 1(a) depicts the concept of a photonic front end where an optical modulator is connected directly to a receive-mode antenna. There are numerous advantages to this implementation of photonics as opposed to an all-RF front end including increased bandwidth, invulnerability to electronic interference, higher power handling and better dynamic range. While a photonic link does offer larger compression and spur-free dynamic range (SFDR) than a typical low-noise RF amplifier, a comparable noise figure can be quite challenging to achieve. A previous work surveyed the state of the art for low-noise-figure photonic links [1], which can employ a variety of schemes. The most prevalent architectures employ a Mach-Zehnder modulator (MZM) as shown in Fig. 1(a).

The utility of high-power photodiodes in low-noise-figure photonic front ends can be demonstrated by considering the noise factor for a link as shown in Fig. 1(a). For an ideal such link with the MZM biased at quadrature, the noise factor can be written as

$$F = 1 + \frac{2V_{\pi}^2}{\pi^2 R_i} \left(\frac{2}{I_{dc}^2 R_o} + \frac{e}{I_{dc} kT} \right), \quad (1)$$

where V_{π} is the half wave voltage for the MZM, R_i is the input resistance, I_{dc} is the average photocurrent, R_o is the output resistance, e is the electron charge constant, k is Boltzmann's constant and T is the temperature. In (1) it is assumed that shot noise and thermal noise are the only contributors to the total noise. The first term in (1) accounts for shot noise at the input of the link, the second term is due to thermal noise at the output and the last term is for shot noise. Very low noise figures are achievable with current state of the art photodiodes which can generate 28 dBm or more of RF power [2], assuming that enough shot-noise-limited laser power can be passed through a MZM to achieve the I_{dc} values.

HIGH DYNAMIC RANGE PHOTONIC SIGNAL PROCESSING

Photonics offers many tools to augment signal processing, even as simple delay lines for remoting or buffering. In certain applications a multi-octave photonic link will feed a RF back end divided into multiple single-octave channels. As shown in Fig. 1(b), the RF back end may eventually be digitized by an array of high-performance, narrow-band analog-to-digital converters. In such cases, the multi-octave photonic SFDR must exceed the SFDR of each channel, often a stringent requirement. Photodiode distortion can significantly degrade the intrinsic SFDR [3].

The change in third-order SFDR is given as [4] $\Delta\text{SFDR}_3 = \left(1 + 4I_{\text{dc}}^2 R_o / \text{OIP}_{3\text{pd}}\right)$, where $\text{OIP}_{3\text{pd}}$ is the photodiode third-order output intercept point. The impact of photodiode second-order distortion can be greater than that of third-order distortion. The photodiode second-order output intercept point required to maintain the SFDR (2) is [4]

$$\text{OIP}_{2\text{pd}} \geq I_{\text{dc}}^{8/2} R_o^{4/3} B^{-1/3} \left(\frac{I_{\text{dc}}^2 \pi^2 R_i R_o kT}{4V_\pi^2} + kT + \frac{eI_{\text{dc}} R_o}{2} \right)^{-1/3}. \quad (2)$$

Photodiode distortion cannot be neglected in photonic links and the equations above provide a starting point for analysis. Techniques can be employed to circumvent photodiode distortion such as arraying photodiodes or using balanced receivers to reject even-order terms [5]. Previously, small deviations in quadrature were shown to cause significant degradations in link OIP2 [4]. However, the MZM can be utilized to offset the photodiode distortion to increase the overall link OIP2 [6]. The cancellation is carried out with a typical link similar to Fig. 1(a) without the resistor and antenna. Using a dual output MZM, a photodiode is connected to one of the outputs and the MZM bias is adjusted to match the amplitude of the photodiode second-order distortion, which for certain operating conditions will be out of phase with the photodiode-generated second-order distortion.

POWER AMPLIFICATION STAGES

A final application of power photodiodes discussed here is for RF amplification [Fig. 1(c)]. The RF gain factor for the link can be written as $g = \pi^2 I_{\text{dc}}^2 R_i R_o / (4V_\pi^2)$, which can be exceed unity if I_{dc} is large enough for a given V_π . Of particular interest is the photodiode power conversion efficiency (PCE) [7],

$$\eta_\omega \equiv \frac{P_\omega}{P_{\text{bias}} + P_{\text{opt}}} = \frac{P_\omega}{I_{\text{dc}} |V_{\text{bias}}| + I_{\text{dc}} / \Re_{\text{eff}}}, \quad (3)$$

where P_ω is the average fundamental power delivered to the load, P_{bias} is the power dissipated by the photodiode bias, P_{opt} is the optical power delivered to the photodiode, V_{bias} is the bias voltage and $\Re_{\text{eff}}$ is the effective responsivity. Note that (3) concentrates on the photodiode in that it does not account for inefficiencies in generating the optical power. Novel techniques can be employed to increase the PCE such as described in [7], where MZM shaping was employed to increase the PCE by 10%.

CONCLUSIONS

The performance of high-power photodiodes continues to advance, driven by needs such as those described here. Varied features of photodiodes determine the capabilities in systems applications, such as power handling, linearity and efficiency. However, these metrics are largely coupled and a single high-power device may meet the requirements for many different applications.

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